

Triggered by Light and Magnetism: Smart Foam PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ Scaffolds for Heat-Controlled Biomedical Applications

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Abstract

The ternary composite foam materials containing PLLA, HAP (20 nm), and morphologically controlled Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (80 nm) were fabricated using the thermally induced phase separation (TIPS) technique over a broad concentration range of the magnetic component (1 – 30 wt%). The foam scaffolds were highly porous (>95%) and lightweight, with a high capacity for soaking in Ringer's solution. The foam density varied with the inorganic component content, ranging from 0.02 to 0.079 g/mL, while the mean pore size was approximately 330 μm. The magnetic behavior of Fe₃O₄ nanocubes and foam composites was characterized. The presence of the inorganic filler caused a shift towards a lower decomposition temperature of PLLA. The energy conversion of both dry and Ringer's solution-soaked foams was studied in detail, demonstrating that the fabricated ternary composites are highly temperature-responsive under the influence of an alternating magnetic field (AMF), near-infrared (NIR) laser radiation (808, 880, and 1122 nm), and the synergistic effect of both external stimuli. This synergy resulted in faster heating and a higher maximum temperature ($T_{max} \approx 80^{\circ}\text{C}$). Biological characterization and heating ability analysis enabled the selection of the most reliable foam, which contained 15% magnetic filler, based on its appropriate microstructure, sufficient biocompatibility, and ability to reach biologically relevant temperatures under AMF exposure and the combined action of NIR and AMF. The fabricated materials exhibit high potential for biomedical applications as well as other areas requiring temperature-controlled stimulation of various processes.

Keywords: ferrites, multifunctional nanomaterials, foams, magnetic hybrids, energy conversion.

1. Introduction

Composites are considered among the most promising and modern future materials as they allow for the flexible integration of different compounds and combine physicochemical properties of their components within the same construct¹⁻³. An example of such materials includes hybrids composed of naturally derived polymers (chitosan, collagen, glucan, polylactide, etc.), which upon integration with inorganic substances of the apatite family, *i.e.*, hydroxyapatites, fluorapatites, carbonated apatites, calcium and/or strontium phosphates, *etc.* enable the development of advanced bone substitute scaffolds for regenerative medicine⁴⁻¹⁰. The ability to use various apatite compounds and their different properties in biological media allows control over new bone tissue formation, which is one of their key advantages¹¹⁻¹³. Polymeric materials are often used as a matrix that maintains the appropriate microstructure of the bone replacement material, serving as a scaffold for newly colonizing cells. In the case of bone tissue, apatites combined with polymers facilitate achieving the desired properties of implants by stimulation of remodeling processes, integration with bone tissue as well as affect mechanical properties and degradability¹. An important aspect of composite materials is their microstructure, which significantly determines whether the scaffold can be applied to compact or cancellous (spongy) bone. Spongy bones are commonly found at the ends of long bones, within flat bones, and inside short bones and are characterized by a highly porous structure with pore sizes ranging from 150 to 800 μm ¹⁴. Polymers and their composites containing inorganic materials with a foam-like microstructure represent an innovative solution for modern implants whereas their microstructure, porosity and other critical parameters can be controlled during the fabrication process¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

The PLLA is a well-known biodegradable polymer widely used in tissue engineering due to its favorable mechanical properties and high biocompatibility. PLLA can be processed into various structures, such as scaffolds and films, that support cell growth and tissue formation¹⁸. Calcium hydroxyapatite (HAP) is a key component of bone tissue, making it an ideal material for bone regeneration and repair. Its biocompatibility and osteoconductive properties are well-documented, and support cell adhesion and proliferation in tissue engineering applications¹⁹. On the other hand, a combination of PLLA with HAP can lead to an increase in the mechanical strength and bioactivity of the resulting composite materials, making them suitable for load-bearing applications in bone regeneration²⁰. There are several techniques for the fabrication of the hybrid organic-inorganic composite towards highly porous materials,

namely, solvent casting and thermally induced phase separation (TIPS), microsphere sintering, selective polymer extraction, gas foaming, 3-D printing, and many more^{21,22}.

A very interesting idea is to use magnetic compounds as a functional additive to polymeric or inorganic scaffolds, such as ferrites (MFe_2O_4 , $M = Co^{2+}, Mn^{2+}, Ni^{2+}, Fe^{2+}, Zn^{2+}$)^{2,3} as a functional additive to polymeric or inorganic scaffolds. The main advantage of magnetic nanoparticles is their ability to generate heat under the action of external stimuli, *i.e.*, alternating magnetic field (AMF) or near-infrared light, which makes them very useful in magneto-photothermal therapies^{2,23–25}. The mechanisms of heat generation vary strongly depending on the type of stimulation. In the case of the AMF, three main contributions to heat induction were identified (1) hysteresis losses, (2) generation of eddy currents, and (3) residual losses that include Néel's internal and Brownian external losses²⁶. Meanwhile, temperature effects associated with NIR light interaction are predominantly caused by non-radiative processes that lead to energy dissipation (lattice vibrations)^{25,27}. Both forms of magnetic nanoparticles stimulation (AMF and NIR) allow the achievement of relevant temperature ranges that affect biological processes ($<43^\circ C$) or can lead to cancer cell elimination ($>43^\circ C$)^{27–30}. Literature review reports mainly on binary organic-inorganic composites of PLLA/ Fe_3O_4 ^{31–39}, HAP/ Fe_3O_4 ^{40, 41} ceramic materials or HAP embedded iron apatite⁴² for enhancing cellular activity, cell adhesion, biocompatibility, mechanical properties, and only a few are devoted to the temperature effects, mainly focused on the interaction with the AMF. In the context of the ternary hybrids PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 of any form, there is no data on their responsiveness to AMF and NIR. Some results can be found for other type of polymer like collagen/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 ⁴³ (AMF only), chitosan/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 ⁴⁴ (no AMF and NIR), PLA/ENR/ Fe_3O_4 ³⁶ (ENR – epoxidized rubber) shape memory triggered by AMF and NIR, PLLA/PGA/ Fe_3O_4 ³⁸ (PGA – polyglycolic acid, AMF only), polycaprolactone/HAP/HAP:Fe⁴² (AMF only), cellulose/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 ⁴⁵ (no AMF and NIR). Therefore, the engineering of new, multifunctional composite materials is necessary and can open attractive directions for possible practical applications.

In this work poly(L-lactic acid) polymer (PLLA) with calcium hydroxyapatite ($Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$) nanoparticles foams were incorporated with morphologically controlled cubic nanomagnetite (80 nm Fe_3O_4) particles to achieve highly AMF and NIR temperature responsive composites characterized by the porous microstructure for potential use in biomedicine related field.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis procedure of magnetic foams preparation

The synthesis of magnetic foams with incorporated magnetite cubic nanoparticles, calcium hydroxyapatite, and polylactide polymer was carried out in three distinct steps: (I) preparation of morphology-controlled Fe_3O_4 cubic nanoparticles, (II) synthesis of nano-sized $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, and (III) integration of the inorganic components into the polylactide matrix to fabricate magnetic and light-responsive functional foam hybrids.

(I) Synthesis of magneto and light temperature-responsive Fe_3O_4 nanocubes.

For the preparation of magnetite cubic particles, the well-known thermal decomposition method reported by Kim et al.⁴⁶ was adopted with minor modifications. In a typical procedure, 2 mmol of the iron(III) complex (iron(III) acetylacetonate, $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$, 99.7%, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) was mixed with 10 mL of dibenzyl ether (BE, 98%, Sigma Aldrich, Poland) in a three-neck glass flask until the substrate was completely dissolved. Subsequently, 4 mmol (1.4 mL) of oleic acid (OA, 90%, Sigma Aldrich, Poland) was added to the reaction mixture. All operations involving the iron source and reaction solution were performed under an inert N_2 atmosphere (99.999%, Linde, Poland) using a glove box (GS Glove Box Systemtechnik GmbH P10R250T2, Germany) equipped with an automatic gas control unit. The flask containing all necessary chemicals was then assembled into a reaction setup comprising a mechanical stirrer, a temperature controller with a Pt-100 sensor (LTR 2500, Juchheim, Germany), a heating mantle, an Allihn's condenser column, and N_2 support gas line. In addition, the N_2 was passed through laboratory scrubbers containing mineral oil and molecular sieves (separately). After that, a solution was degassed with N_2 for 60 min at room temperature. Subsequently, the reaction mixture temperature was increased to 285°C and left for an additional 30 min under constant stirring and a protective N_2 atmosphere. The final mother liquor with visible black precipitate was cooled down to room temperature and further separated by centrifugation and washing cycles with the solvent mixture containing hexane/acetone/ethanol (1:1:1 v/v ratio, all delivered by Chempur, Poland, pure for analysis). The resulting magnetic particles were resuspended in ethanol and stored in a laboratory refrigerator. Nanoparticle concentration in a suspension was determined using a microbalance technique with a Radwag MYA 5.4Y scale by filling up an aluminum foil crucible

with 50 μL of particle dispersion and solvent evaporation until dry mass. Three repetitions were done, and an average mass value was calculated.

(II) Preparation of calcium nanohydroxyapatite polymer filler

For the fabrication of $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ inorganic nanoparticles, a well-known precipitation technique proposed by Rodriguez-Lorenzo *et al.*⁴⁷ was employed, with modified process parameters to obtain smaller particles. Briefly, to prepare approximately 100 g of hydroxyapatite, 1 mol (236.15 g) of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%, Sigma Aldrich, Poland) and 0.6 mol (79.23 g) of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (99%, Sigma Aldrich, Poland) were used, maintaining a Ca:P ratio of 1.66. Both salts were separately dissolved in deionized water in glass beakers. The phosphate-containing solution was then slowly added to the calcium nitrate solution, leading to the rapid precipitation of a white powder. Vigorous stirring, preferably mechanical for large batches, was essential to prevent powder adhesion and dense material formation. During mixing, a 25% NH_4OH solution (99%, Avantor, Poland) was added in 20 mL portions to keep a strongly basic pH above 9. This step was crucial for transforming the initially precipitated apatite into a hydroxyapatite structure. Maintaining the pH above 9 was particularly important, as a neutral pH could lead to the formation of a TCP/HAP mixture⁴⁸. The presence of biphasic apatite can be desirable in certain cases to adjust phosphate resorption rates for bone integration processes in apatite-based implants⁴⁹. The whole mixing stage lasted approximately 2 h, with continuous pH monitoring. The product was then separated via centrifugation and washed with Milli-Q water to purify it and remove ammonium nitrate by-product, which accounted for nearly half of the total mixture. Purification was critical for safety reasons, preventing the risk of explosion and NO_x contamination during thermal treatment. However, the separated NH_4NO_3 could be collected and reused as a key ingredient in plant fertilizers. Finally, the resulting white powder was dried at 60°C for 24 h and annealed at 500°C for 3 h. Due to significant particle aggregation caused by sintering, a final milling step was performed to enhance sample uniformity. The primary advantage of this protocol lies in scalability, enabling large-scale hydroxyapatite production.

(III) Fabrication of functional foam hybrid materials

The integration of inorganic components, magneto-light-responsive Fe_3O_4 cubic nanoparticles, and bioresorbable HAP nanoparticles into the PLLA matrix was carried out by using the TIPS technique supported with SLP (salt-leaching process). Further details on this

approach can be found elsewhere⁵⁰. However, for this study, the process parameters were significantly modified. Specifically, PLLA (Resomer L210s, Evonik, Germany), along with the previously prepared HAP and cubic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, served as substrates. In the standard procedure, PLLA and HAP in a 50:50 weight ratio were suspended in 1,4-dioxane (99%, Sigma Aldrich, Poland) at 75°C under mechanical stirring overnight, ensuring the formation of a homogeneous mixture. Subsequently, different amounts of Fe₃O₄ in dioxane were added to achieve magnetic particle concentrations ranging from 1 to 30 wt%. The final solution was mixed vigorously with a stirrer and placed on a shaker to eliminate air bubbles. Sodium chloride (NaCl, Stanlab, Poland) with an average particle size of 500 µm was used as a porogen. After mixing, the blend was dispensed into a 24-wells plate (0.5 mL/well) and frozen at -40°C for 24 h. This was followed by freeze-drying at -50°C under a vacuum of 10 Pa for an additional 24 h to form porous foams. In the final step, foams, including the reference sample without Fe₃O₄, were subjected to SLP, which was repeated multiple times with fresh water exchange to ensure NaCl removal. Washing effectiveness was confirmed by the reaction of the AgNO₃ solution with the supernatant to verify the absence of Cl⁻ anions. Final foam composites were dried at 40°C for 24 h and used for physicochemical and biological characterization.

2.3. Characterization of physicochemical properties of fabricated materials

The X-ray powder diffraction technique (XRD) was employed to study the structural properties of the stock Fe₃O₄ magnetite and HAP particles as well as fabricated foams. All diffraction patterns were recorded using a Bruker D8 Advanced diffractometer with an X-ray source copper lamp ($K_{\alpha 1}$ 1.54060 Å) within a 2θ range of 15-65°. In addition, a Ni filter was utilized to filter out $K_{\alpha 2}$ associated reflections. In the case of highly X-ray-absorbing Fe₃O₄ particles and foams with incorporated magnetite, the data curation relied on background correction (Diffrac.Eva software (V.2)), normalization, and signal smoothing (Origin Pro 9, Origin Lab). The final results were compared with the reference cards from the ICDD database (International Centre for Diffraction Data). Sample preparation involved the evaporation of part of the ethanol suspension of Fe₃O₄ to a dry powder. No special treatment for HAP and foam measurements was used.

Magnetite and calcium hydroxyapatite particle size, morphology, and distribution were determined by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with a Tecnai Osiris X-FEG HRTEM microscope (FEI Company, USA) operating at 200 kV. Sample preparation required

placing a droplet of the ethanol-based nanoparticle suspensions of all inorganic materials (0.25 mg/ml) on a carbon-coated 200 mesh copper grids (EM Resolutions, United Kingdom) and slow drying overnight at room temperature under dust protection.

In the case of the foam hybrids, microstructure imaging was carried out using a Tescan Vega 3 (Tescan Group, Czech Republic) scanning electron microscope. The sample was deposited to the carbon tape, mounted on an aluminum stage, and placed in the microscope chamber. Due to the risk of polymer melting, a low-voltage regime was used (max 5 kV). The size distribution analysis of Fe₃O₄, HAP particles, and pore diameter was performed using freeware ImageJ software (ver. 1.46r). The density and porosity of foams were measured using a hydrostatic balance Shimadzu AX 220 (Shimadzu Ltd., Japan). The porosity was calculated with the following formula:

$$\Phi_p = \left[1 - \frac{\rho_{sc}}{\rho_b}\right], (1)$$

where Φ_p is porosity, ρ_{sc} represents scaffold density, and ρ_b is the bulk density of polymer. Both ρ_{sc} and ρ_b (1.24 g/mL) were measured by the buoyancy method.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was employed to analyze the structural features of the fabricated foams. Thermo Scientific Nicolet iZ10 spectrometer equipped with an attenuated total reflection (ATR) accessory. Spectra were recorded over a range of 2000 - 500 cm⁻¹. Before measurement, a standard calibration procedure was performed to correct for air humidity. No special sample treatment was required. Samples were directly placed on the diamond crystal and pressed against the hot-spot using a bolt.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) were performed using a TGA/DSC1 Mettler Toledo system under N₂ atmosphere. For each foam sample, 5 mg of material was taken and heated from 50°C to 550°C at a heating rate of 20°C/min. Data from the TGA characterization were processed with STARe software and plotted in Origin 9.0. Composite glass transition and crystallization temperatures were determined utilizing a DSC apparatus coupled with a TC 100 intercooler under an inert N₂ atmosphere (30 mL/min). For this purpose, approximately 6 mg of foam was placed inside an aluminum pan and heated from 0°C to 200°C at a rate of 5°C/min. Afterward, sample was cooled down to 0°C, and a reheating scan was performed to eliminate the foam's thermal history and evaluate thermal transitions.

Magnetic measurements were performed using a Quantum Design MPMS7XL superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer. Zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) magnetization curves were recorded during warming from 3 K to 350 K under an applied magnetic field of 10 mT. Isothermal magnetization measurements were conducted at 3 K and 300 K with magnetic fields ranging from -5 T to +5 T. To prevent physical rotation of the magnetic nanoparticles during measurements, the samples were immobilized within gelatin capsules using a small amount of adhesive. The organic content, originating from surfactant residues and the PLLA matrix, was quantified by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) for each sample, and the magnetization data were subsequently corrected based on the inorganic (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticle mass.

Heat generation ability of magnetite containing foams as well as reference PLLA/HAP sample, was measured using two external stimuli, namely alternating magnetic field (AMF) and near-infrared laser radiation (NIR, 808, 880, and 1122 nm) under separate and synergy mode. G2 D5 Series Multimode 1500 W driver (nanoScale Biomagnetics, Spain) equipped with a thermally insulated S32 coil was used (polystyrene box). In the case of laser stimulation, 808 nm, 880 nm, and 1122 nm continuous laser modules (power stability no worse than 1%) equipped with 400 μm optical fibers (CNI, China) were utilized. Lasers were calibrated with an Ophir StarLite power meter using a beam track thermal sensor 10 A-PPS (Ophir, Israel) with a measurable laser power range of 20 mW - 10 W, with laser beam size detection accuracy of 5%. The magnetic field frequency and intensity were chosen between 145 - 396 kHz and 22 - 32 kA/m, while laser output power for all three wavelengths was between 100 - 600 mW. All measurements were done on dry and Ringer's solution soaked foams (2 h at room temperature), mimicking conditions at possible implantation sites. Temperature effects were recorded with a FLIR T660 scientific thermovision camera (FLIR, USA) and analyzed with dedicated ResearchIR software (FLIR, USA). The final data presentation was performed in Origin 9.0 software.

2.5. Cell culture experiments

The normal human fetal osteoblast cell line (hFOB 1.19, American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), USA) was used to assess cytotoxicity through both indirect and direct methods, as well as to evaluate cell proliferation. Cells were cultured in a 1:1 mixture of DMEM/Ham's F12 medium without phenol red (Gibco Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), supplemented with 10%

fetal bovine serum (Pan-Biotech GmbH, Germany), 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin, and 300 µg/mL G418 (Sigma-Aldrich, Poland). The cells were maintained at 34°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere.

2.5.1. Evaluation of cytotoxicity by indirect method

Cytotoxicity was assessed using the MTT assay, in accordance with ISO 10993-5, using extracts of biomaterials prepared according to ISO 10993-12. In summary, extracts were obtained by incubating 25 mg of the composites in 1 mL of culture medium, which was dictated by the high capacity of the materials to absorb fluids, at 37°C for 24 h. Concurrently, a negative control for cytotoxicity was prepared. Cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells/mL and cultured at 34°C for 24 h. Subsequently, the medium was replaced with 100 µL of the respective foam extracts, and the cells were incubated for an additional 24 h. After incubation, an MTT colorimetric assay (Sigma-Aldrich, Poland) was performed to evaluate cell viability and metabolic activity. Briefly, 25 µL of MTT solution (5 mg MTT/1 mL PBS) was added to each well and incubated for 3 h at 34°C to allow mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzymes in viable cells to reduce MTT to formazan. As a result of this reduction, formazan accumulated as crystals within the living cells. After the specified incubation period, 100 µL of 10% SDS solution in 0.01M HCl was added to each well to dissolve the formazan crystals. After 12 h, the absorbance of the referred to solubilized formazan concentration was measured using a plate reader at a wavelength of 570 nm. The amount of formazan is proportional to the number of viable cells. The results of the MTT assay were expressed as a percentage of the optical density (OD) value obtained relative to the negative control for cytotoxicity. Cytotoxicity was also assessed qualitatively with the Live/Dead Double Staining Kit (Sigma-Aldrich, Poland) following the manufacturer's protocol. The hFOB 1.19 cells treated with biomaterials extracts were stained with fluorescent dyes and observed utilizing a confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM, Olympus Fluoview equipped with FV1000, Japan)

2.5.2. Evaluation of cytotoxicity by direct method

In order to assess cytotoxicity using the direct method, hFOB 1.19 cells were seeded directly onto the materials at a density of 5×10^4 cells/mL. After 48 hours of culture, the cells were stained with the Live/Dead Double Staining Kit (Sigma-Aldrich, Poland), following the manufacturer's protocol. Subsequently, the samples were visualized with a confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM, Olympus Fluoview equipped with FV1000, Poland).

2.5.3. Evaluation of cell proliferation

The impact of biomaterial extracts on cell proliferation was assessed both qualitatively and quantitatively using the following procedure. Cell line at a density of 5×10^4 cells/mL was seeded in a volume of 100 μ L into 96-well plates and incubated in a culture medium with 10% FBS for 24 h at 34°C. On the following day, the culture medium was replaced with biomaterial extracts (prepared at a ratio of 25 mg of composite per 1 mL of 10% culture medium). The experiment was conducted over 5 days with two time points for the evaluation of cell proliferation. Specifically, on days 3 and 5, the cell number was determined employing the Cell Counting Kit-8 (WST-8 assay, Sigma-Aldrich, Poland) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Simultaneously, at the same time points, the cells were fixed in a 3.7% formaldehyde solution and permeabilized with 0.2% Triton X-100 solution. They were then stained with the fluorescent dyes Hoechst 33342 and AlexaFluor™ 635 Phalloidin to visualize actin cytoskeleton fibers and cell nuclei. The samples were observed using confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM, Olympus Fluoview equipped with FV1000, Japan) for a qualitative evaluation of cell growth over time.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterization of stock nanoparticles and foams

The structural phase identification of the stock Fe_3O_4 and HAP nanoparticles, as well as the representative foam, was carried out using the X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique (Fig. 1). The diffraction patterns for Fe_3O_4 and HAP were compared with reference diffraction standard cards no. 19-0629 and 09-0432 from the ICDD international database, respectively. Both compounds exhibited a very good agreement with characteristic crystalline phase reflections, confirming their structures as magnetite and hydroxyapatite, respectively. In the case of the PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foam, the diffraction pattern reveals a combination of the primary characteristic peaks of all its constituents. The PLLA is classified as a semicrystalline polymer, and it can exist in several crystalline forms (α , α' , β , γ). The inset in Fig. 1 highlights typical signals observed within the 15 - 25° 2θ range. These features, especially at around 17° and 19° 2θ are indicative of the α PLLA crystalline phase^{51,52} and are clearly visible in the composite material as well. The obtained result supported evidence of the successful integration of all compounds in the hybrid material.

Figure 1. X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the stock Fe_3O_4 , HAP particles, and PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 . The inset shows a pattern of the neat PLLA polymer.

The primary particle size, its distribution, and morphological characteristics of stock Fe_3O_4 and HAP particles were analyzed using TEM (Fig. 2). The magnetite nanoparticles predominantly showed a cubic morphology with an average size of approximately 80 nm. In contrast, the hydroxyapatite particles formed a finer-grained product with a mean size of 23 nm. Unlike Fe_3O_4 , HAP crystallites demonstrated a tendency to adopt elongated shapes, highlighting a distinct difference in their growth behavior.

Figure 3 presents a representative photo of the actual PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 5% composite sample, showing that the foam is magnetically responsive. The sample floated on the water surface, which is an indication of its low density. The final composite foams were prepared with a broad concentration of Fe_3O_4 ranging from 1 up to 30% to study the effect of magnetic components on microstructure (together with HAP), heat generation ability, and biological activity.

Foams microstructure was analyzed using the SEM technique. A representative image of the PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 composite was shown in Fig. 4. As one can see the hybrid material exhibited a significant porosity, with an average pore size of $329 \pm 53 \mu\text{m}$, which corresponded to the size of the NaCl porogen used during the fabrication process. In addition, smaller pores (below $50 \mu\text{m}$) were observed, particularly within the foam wall areas. Their formation is likely attributed to solvent (dioxane) evaporation during the foam processing. The signs of the

microstructure collapse were detected upon a significant increase in the inorganic content (above 70% - HAP and Fe_3O_4).

Figure 2. TEM images of the Fe_3O_4 and HAP nanoparticles and their size distribution histograms.

Figure 3. Photograph of the representative PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foam with 5% of the magnetic component.

Figure 4. SEM images of the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 5% and PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 20% composite foam materials.

The density of foams with varying Fe₃O₄ and HAP nanoparticle content was measured using a hydrostatic balance. Subsequently, porosity was calculated, and the results were summarized in Table 1. The PLLA foam shows the lowest scaffold density (0.0208 g/mL), while the incorporation of HAP (3.16 g/mL bulk) slightly increases the skeletal density (0.0267 g/mL). A progressive increase in the Fe₃O₄ (5.17 g/mL) concentration led to higher density. Notably, a significant change occurs at Fe₃O₄ concentrations exceeding 10%, where the scaffold density nearly quadruples (from 0.0208 to 0.0790 g/mL). Foam porosity remains relatively unchanged, with only an approximate 3% variation when comparing a PLLA matrix containing 20% Fe₃O₄. However, the highest difference is observed at 30% of Fe₃O₄ (80% of total HAP and Fe₃O₄), where porosity reaches 93% and is caused by ongoing microstructure collapse. These findings are consistent with Szustakiewicz *et al.*⁵⁰ on PLLA/HAP scaffolds fabricated using the same approach.

Table 1. The density and porosity of the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams with different concentrations of magnetite.

Sample	Porosity Φ_p (%)	Density ρ_{sc} (g/mL)
PLLA	98.32	0.021 ± 0.012
PLLA/HAP	97.85	0.027 ± 0.002
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 1%	97.77	0.028 ± 0.006
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 5%	97.35	0.033 ± 0.011
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 10%	96.55	0.043 ± 0.009
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 15%	95.99	0.050 ± 0.004
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 20%	95.44	0.057 ± 0.007
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 30%	93.62	0.080 ± 0.011

The PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams with a concentration of magnetite above 20% are notably stiffer, showing the first signs of microstructural degradation. The observed changes in porosity and density suggest that the incorporation of HAP and Fe₃O₄ into PLLA composites leads to denser structures with reduced porosity when the total inorganic content exceeds 80%. Highly concentrated foams are brittle and prone to fracture (above 70% of Fe₃O₄ and HAP). However, foams below 20% of the magnetite will show potential for cell colonization and proliferation due to the high porosity and preferential pore size.

Figure 5. The FTIR-ATR spectra of the Fe₃O₄, HAP stock nanoparticles, and PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams with different magnetite concentrations. Red lines show main HAP vibrations, while the black line corresponds to Fe-O mode.

FTIR-ATR spectroscopy was employed to study the structural features as well as surface properties of the Fe₃O₄, HAP, and PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams (Fig. 5). For the stock cubic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, typical broad and high-intensity vibration mode was recorded within the range of the 680 - 500 cm⁻¹ associated with the Fe-O characteristic for tetrahedrally coordinated iron cation⁵³. The spectra of the HAP nanoparticles prepared by the precipitation technique show characteristic bands ascribed to the PO₄³⁻ and OH⁻ groups vibrations⁵⁴. Therefore, the modes with maxima at around 1091, 1023, and 964 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the stretching vibrations, while at 601 and 564 cm⁻¹ correspond with bending modes associated with the ν_3 , ν_1 , and ν_4 vibrations, respectively. The prominent band at around 630 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of the hydroxyl unit vibrations in the HAP structure. In the case of the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams, there are several features. The first one was associated with the occurrence of bands related to the organic polymer matrix PLLA. The following vibration bands attribution was made, namely 1756 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1455 cm⁻¹ (C-H), 1381 and 1359 cm⁻¹ (C-H), 1181 cm⁻¹ (C-O), 1129 cm⁻¹ (C-O), 870 and 754 cm⁻¹ (CH₃). The spectral features of the PLLA are in good agreement with the literature data^{51,52,55}. Integration of inorganic compounds into the PLLA matrix resulted mainly in a visible shift of the PO₄³⁻ modes, being evidence of interaction with the organic material. We observed that the contribution of the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles results in the peak broadening between 630 - 500 cm⁻¹ for elevated concentrations. Moreover, bands at 630 and 600 cm⁻¹ associated with HAP modes diminished or were covered by the intense Fe-O, and strong ν_4 (564 cm⁻¹) overlapping vibrations.

The thermal properties of the foam scaffolds were investigated using TGA-DTA and DSC measurements as a function of Fe₃O₄ content, for PLLA/HAP binary composite and PLLA reference foam (Fig. 6 and Fig. 7). Generally, PLLA undergoes complete decomposition between 328°C and 410°C, with a peak centered at 372°C. The addition of HAP to the polymer did not significantly alter the decomposition temperature. However, the presence of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles caused a notable shift of approximately 30°C toward a lower decomposition temperature (around 340°C). Similar behavior was observed by Yang *et al.* in PLLA/Fe₃O₄³⁹ binary composites as well as upon ZnO nanoparticle addition to the PLLA matrix⁵⁶. Both authors attributed the temperature shift to the expansion of the interface space and the possible catalytic activity of nanoparticles, which decreased polymer thermal stability. It was found that the initial decomposition temperature of foams changed significantly. It is worth noting that the decomposition of PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ scaffolds was not only faster but also had

a narrower temperature range. This suggests that magnetite nanoparticles may act as catalysts or oxidants, accelerating PLLA depolymerization at lower temperatures.

Figure 6. TGA (left panel) and DTA curves (right panel) of the chosen PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams as a function of magnetite concentration.

Figure 7. The 1st heating DSC curves (a), the cooling DSC curves (b), and the 2nd heating DSC curves of PLLA/HAP and PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams.

Analysis of the DSC results (Fig. 7) shows three distinct thermal effects, namely glass transition (T_g) within a temperature range of 61 - 69°C, cold crystallization around 100°C, and a melting temperature (T_m) between 178 - 185°C. During the 1st heating, a slight decrease in glass transition temperature was found, followed by an increase in magnetite concentration. A similar effect was noticed in the melting process, whose temperature peak for binary PLLA/HAP foam was at 185°C and decreased to 181°C for the composite with 20% Fe₃O₄. Upon integrating the magnetic particles into the PLLA/HAP, a noticeable promotion of nucleation in the crystallization process was observed. This phenomenon is particularly evident during heating and cooling cycles. It manifests as an increase in the endothermic and exothermic peaks. During the cooling, one can note that the exotherm peak is monomodal with a maximum of around 100°C for all foams. We did not observe a bimodal shape of the exothermic peak (two T_c temperatures) and their shift towards higher temperatures (up to 119°C) upon HAP amount increase as reported by Szustakiewicz⁵⁰. In this study, the T_c remained stable. We believe that this is probably due to the different character of the interaction of magnetite particles. They did not significantly alter the crystallization of the PLLA polymer, like HAP. A similar observation was reported by Laraba *et al.*⁵² with graphene oxide (GO) as a filler of the PLLA matrix. However, GO shifted the melting temperature toward higher values. Interestingly, in the plot representing the 2nd heating, one can distinguish an exothermic peak with a maximum of around 161°C. In accordance with literature data, this behavior is associated with the phase transition of α' to α form of PLLA, meaning that composite foams consist of a mixture of both PLLA structures⁵⁷. The former one was not detected by XRD, probably due to its low content and the instrument's sensitivity. Moreover, the rise of concentration of magnetic particles led to an increase in the exothermic peak surface area, indicating the effect of Fe₃O₄ on the formation of a greater amount of the α crystalline phase.

ZFC and FC magnetization curves (Fig. 8) exhibit a bifurcation above 350 K, indicating that all samples remain in a magnetically blocked state throughout the entire measured temperature range⁵⁸. This behavior is consistent with the critical size for single-domain Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (approximately 91 nm)^{59,60}. The ZFC curves display a pronounced drop in magnetization around 100 K, which is attributed to the Verwey transition⁶¹ - a phenomenon characteristic of magnetite and absent in maghemite. No significant shift in the Verwey transition temperature was detected with increasing Fe₃O₄ nanocubes concentration in the

PLLA matrix, suggesting that interparticle interactions remain relatively weak and do not significantly influence the transition behavior. Isothermal magnetization measurements at 3 K reveal moderate coercivity ($\mu_0 H_c \approx 0.04$ T, or 400 Oe)⁴⁶ across all samples (Fig. 8). The saturation magnetization values (83, 97, 87, and 94 $\text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$ for 1%, 5%, 10%, and 15% Fe_3O_4 loading, respectively) remain close to that of bulk magnetite ($M_s \approx 90 \text{Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$), indicating the high crystallinity and preservation of the magnetic properties of the Fe_3O_4 nanocubes. At room temperature, the isothermal magnetization curves exhibit very low coercivity, further supporting the presence of a blocked magnetic state for the Fe_3O_4 nanocubes under ambient conditions.

Figure 8. ZFC/FC magnetization curves (a) of Fe_3O_4 nanocubes and PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foams (dashed line indicates the Verwey transition, T_v) and their isothermal magnetization (b) at 300 K (inset: zoomed 3 K isothermal magnetization).

3. 2. Heating ability of the ternary PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foam composites under AMF and NIR stimulation

The effectiveness of PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foam in converting energy into heat under an alternating magnetic field (AMF) and near-infrared light (NIR) was evaluated for both separate and synergic action (dual mode) of external stimuli. All measurements were conducted as a function of Fe_3O_4 concentration (1 - 30%) and optimized for the magnetic field frequency (149 - 496 kHz), intensity (22 - 32 kA/m, corresponding to 27.6 - 40.2 mT), laser wavelengths (808, 880, 1122 nm), and laser power (100 - 600 mW) for dry and Ringer's solution soaked materials

(Figs. 9 - 13). A binary PLLA/HAP hybrid foam was used as the reference material. Optimization of the external stimulation parameters was performed on a PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ sample containing 8% Fe₃O₄, which resulted in obtaining temperatures exceeding 43°C crucial for potential biological applications.

Figure 9. Heating curves of the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 8% dry foam measured for (a) AMF stimulation, (b) 808 nm laser, (c) 880 nm laser, and (d) 1122 nm laser as a function of the AMF parameters and laser power (separate modes).

The complete characterization of stock Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and their heat-generation capabilities was the subject of our previous study on magneto-plasmonic heterostructures⁶². The Fe₃O₄ concentration dependence in PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ was measured for Ringer's solution-soaked foams by using the following AMF parameters 336 kHz, 27 kA/m (Fig. 10). For dual

mode (synergy) heating experiments were conducted at 336 kHz, 27kA/m, and 600 mW for three wavelengths 808, 880 and 1122 nm covering the Ist and the IInd optical biological window (Fig. 13). In all cases, the cooling stage was recorded for both dry and soaked composites. The optimization of the alternating field parameters and laser power was performed on a dry PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foam containing 8% magnetite cubic particles in order to choose the most reliable conditions for contactless heat generation. As shown in Fig. 9a, the best performance was achieved for the 336 kHz and 27 kA/m (33.9 mT) with a maximum temperature of 54.1°C. The 145 kHz and 32 kA/m (40.2 mT) also gave a high temperature of around 50°C for dry composite. In the case of the laser light, three wavelengths were tested 808, 880, and 1122 nm (see Fig 9b - 9d) for the 100, 200, and 300 mW laser power, respectively. A higher power was not applied since the T_{max} of 93°C was achieved. Therefore, further increasing this parameter might lead to polymer melting and microstructure degradation, which will be seen as a detrimental effect. The variation in the T_{max} (47 - 98°C) for lasers was attributed to the laser light spot size affecting heating ability. All used wavelengths have a capacity for significant heat induction due to the Fe₃O₄ efficient absorption that covers a broad spectral range⁶³.

Table 2. AMF and NIR conversion parameters, *i.e.*, heating speed dT/dt and maximum temperature (T_{max}) for the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 8% dry foam.

Sample	Parameters (AMF and NIR)	dT/dt (°C/s)	T_{max} (°C)
AMF			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	145 kHz, 32 kA/m	1.91	50.3
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	336 kHz, 27 kA/m	2.49	54.1
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	496 kHz, 22 kA/m	1.59	43.5
Laser 808 nm			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	100 mW	6.05	50.5
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	200 mW	18.17	76.5
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	300 mW	25.27	97.6
Laser 880 nm			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	100 mW	4.32	47.7
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	200 mW	9.58	60.2
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	300 mW	15.43	78.3
Laser 1122 nm			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	100 mW	5.10	50.8
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	200 mW	9.17	73.8
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	300 mW	16.32	93.4

A comparison of the heating speed (Table 2) revealed a difference in the effectiveness of the heat generation mechanisms over one order of magnitude. For the AMF stimulation, the dT/dt

is between 1.59 – 2.49°C/s, while laser stimulation led to the values within the range of 5.1-25.2°C/s, showing its superior role over AMF heat induction. However, it has to be stressed that laser light utilization in biomedical applications will be problematic due to tissue penetration limitations, while AMF overcomes this drawback. Therefore, laser light will be limited to on-skin and shallow treatments. For deeper-tissue procedures, more invasive techniques such as laparoscopy must be used^{64,65}. Although, foams are primarily designed for bone tissue replacement, other potential applications, such as wound-healing composites, remain viable. It is of great importance to measure the ability of heat induction in an environment that resembles the implantation site. Therefore, the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams were soaked for 2 h in the Ringer's solution (Table 3), and further characterization of energy conversion was performed (Fig. 10 – 13). The interesting feature of all foams is their ability to water-based solution loading of ≈ 440 - 500%, except for PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ above 20%, when a water loading drops below 400% due to the microstructure degradation. Figure 10 presents the heating curves recorded for the different concentrations of magnetic components (1 - 30%) under stimulation with the optimal AMF (336 kHz, 27 kA/m) parameters.

Table 3. Mass change of the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams before and after soaking with Ringer's solution.

Sample	Foam mass (g)	Ringer's solution soaked foam (g)	Water (g)	Water loading (%)
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 1%	0.0318	0.1612	0.1294	506.9
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 5%	0.0229	0.1230	0.1001	537.1
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 10%	0.0382	0.1694	0.1311	443.2
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 15%	0.0373	0.1988	0.1615	533.0
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 20%	0.0465	0.1902	0.1437	409.2
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 30%	0.0592	0.1803	0.1211	304.6

It is very clear that the presence of a high water loading (Ringer's solution) dramatically affects the heating ability due to the high specific heat capacity of water (4.184 J/g°C). In general, values of the heating speed dT/dt (Table 4) decreased strongly if directly compared to the dT/dt obtained for the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 8% composite (dry foam - 2.49°C/s, soaked foam - 0.07°C/s). It also caused a two-fold decrease of the T_{max} from 54.1°C to 27.8°C. Since the AMF is a key stimulant for deep-tissue penetration, the bottom limit for samples that will allow achieving a biologically relevant temperature was a PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ with 15% of magnetite (43.8°C with dT/dt of 0.52°C/s). In the case of the higher-doped foams, one can see a progressive increase in the T_{max} (up to 74°C) and heating speed (0.52 to 1.39°C/s). However, as mentioned earlier, the degradation of the foam microstructure was already noticed above

20% of the Fe_3O_4 . Thus, only samples with a maximum of 15% of magnetite were considered for further biological evaluation.

Figure 10. Heating curves of the magnetite concentration dependence of the soaked PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foams under the action of the AMF (336 kHz, 27 kA/m).

Table 4. AMF conversion parameters, *i.e.*, heating speed dT/dt and maximum temperature (T_{max}) for the PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 Ringer’s solution soaked foams – concentration dependence.

Sample	dT/dt ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$)	T_{max} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
AMF 336 kHz. 27 kA/m		
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 1%	0.01	22.2
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 2%	0.01	22.9
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 5%	0.025	23.7
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 8%	0.07	27.8
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 10%	0.22	35.5
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 15%	0.52	43.8
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 20%	1.28	58.8
PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 30%	1.39	74.7

To evaluate the effect of laser light stimulation, measuring the dependence of the laser power within the 300 - 600 mW range was necessary. It was anticipated that the presence of water molecules in soaked foams would significantly affect heating efficiency across all three wavelengths (Fig. 11). To ensure a proper comparison, heat induction was analysed using PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foams containing 8% magnetite. The final data are summarized in Table 5. It is evident that the high heat capacity of the solvent strongly influences energy conversion. This phenomenon was reflected in a drastic change of dT/dt values, which ranged from 0.36

to 2.32°C/s for soaked composites (dry 4.32 - 25.27°C/s, T_{max} 43 - 97°C), along with a reduced T_{max} of 33 - 45°C at 8% Fe₃O₄ doping.

Figure 11. Heating curves of the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 8% soaked foam measured for (a) 808 nm, (b) 880 nm, and (c) 1122 nm laser modules as a function of the laser power 300 - 600 mW.

Table 5. NIR conversion parameters, *i.e.*, heating speed dT/dt and maximum temperature (T_{max}) for the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 8% soaked foam.

Sample	Parameters (NIR)	dT/dt (°C/s)	T_{max} (°C)
Laser 808 nm			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	300 mW	0.64	34.5
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	450 mW	1.59	40.8
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	600 mW	2.32	45.2
Laser 880 nm			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	300 mW	0.46	33.2
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	450 mW	0.42	34.7
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	600 mW	1.04	40.2
Laser 1122 nm			
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	300 mW	0.36	33.7
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	450 mW	0.39	38.6
PLLA/HAP/Fe ₃ O ₄ 8%	600 mW	1.35	43.1

Notably, NIR stimulation is significantly more effective than AMF in terms of both heating speed and maximum temperature. This feature is crucial to avoid the induction of cell thermotolerance in hyperthermia applications⁶⁶. The direct comparison of the dry and soaked foams during the action of the NIR light (808, 880, and 1122 nm) was shown in Fig. 12. The concentration dependence of cubic magnetite nanoparticles in PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams was measured under synergy mode. It involved, referred to here as dual mode, a combined action

of AMF and NIR laser light (AMF: 336 kHz, 27 kA/m; NIR: 600 mW at 808, 880, and 1122 nm) for soaked ternary composites (Fig. 13). For the PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ sample with 8% magnetite, the maximum temperature (T_{max}) reached was 49°C (AMF: 27.8°C, NIR₈₀₈: 45°C, NIR₈₈₀: 40°C, NIR₁₁₂₂: 43°C), demonstrating that the synergistic interaction of both stimuli leads to a further temperature increase. As shown, the T_{max} obtained for all foams under dual mode was significantly higher than that achieved with individual stimulation. The highest recorded T_{max} was observed for PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ foams containing 30% magnetite, reaching 84°C (NIR₈₀₈), 80°C (NIR₈₈₀), and 82°C (NIR₁₁₂₂). However, foams with 20% and 30% Fe₃O₄ content exhibited a loss of their microstructure, making them unsuitable for further biological characterization. Figure 14 shows a comparison of different stimulation modes for PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ with 15% magnetite, highlighting striking differences between the various energy conversion mechanisms. Notably, this sample could reach biologically relevant temperature ranges using AMF, NIR, and their synergistic combination.

Figure 12. Comparison of the dT/dt and T_{max} values for the dry, and Ringer's solution-soaked foams with 8% of Fe₃O₄ under NIR stimulation (open symbols - dry, full-colored - soaked foams).

Figure 13. Heating curves of the magnetite concentration dependence under the action of both stimuli (AMF 336 kHz, 27 kA/m, 600 mW, 808, 880, and 1122 nm lasers).

Figure 14. Comparison of the heating generation using different stimuli AMF, and NIR separately and under synergy mode (dual) for different laser wavelengths (808, 880, 1122 nm) on soaked PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 15% foam.

3.3. Assessment of biological interactions with engineered biomaterials

Our studies have shown that extracts from biomaterials composed solely of HAP and PLLA exhibited some cytotoxicity towards hFOB 1.19 cells (Fig. 15). According to ISO 10993-5, biomedical materials are considered cytotoxic when the percentage of viable cells falls below 70%⁶⁷. MTT assay results after 24 h of exposure to extracts from these materials indicated that only extracts containing 15% of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles did not exhibit cytotoxicity achieving a

cell viability of $76.6\% \pm 2.38$. After 48 h of exposure, it was observed that biomaterials containing 10% of Fe_3O_4 also showed no cytotoxicity with a cell viability of $80.2\% \pm 1.2$ while those with a 15% addition achieved an even higher viability level of $91\% \pm 3.2$ (Fig. 15a, 15b). Therefore, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles integration into PLLA/HAP composites enhanced their biological safety in a concentration-dependent manner. We believe that the PLLA/HAP cytotoxicity might be due to the high affinity of metal cations towards the porous material surface. This phenomenon was observed by Fijoł *et al.*⁶⁸, showing enhanced cation chemisorption on the 3D PLLA/HAP (15% of HAP) scaffolds after incorporation of small apatite nanoparticles with extended surface area.

Fig. 15. Cytotoxicity of the extracts derived from the biomaterials as well as from polystyrene (PS), which served as the control extract: (a), (b) after 24 and 48 h of incubation hFOB cell viability (MTT assay). Statistically significant differences were observed compared to the control extract (Two-Way ANOVA test followed by a Bonferroni comparison test $P < 0.05$); (c), (d) images obtained using a confocal laser scanning microscope presenting live/dead staining of cells after exposure to extracts from the tested biomaterials (green fluorescence - live cells, red fluorescence - dead cells). Magnification 100x, scale bar 100 μm . Similar behavior was reported by Klimek *et al.*⁶⁹ on high specific area HAP ceramics that caused significant false-toxicity due to the depletion of the medium from the important ions through a strong adsorption to the surface of HAP (35 nm particles). They proposed a modified protocol for the estimation of biomaterial cytotoxicity. However, this approach was not used

by us, since the most valuable composite from the biological point of view was PLLA/HAP/Fe₃O₄ 15% foam that showed no effect on hFOB cells.

The Live/Dead staining confirmed the results of the MTT assay, clearly demonstrating a significantly higher number of viable cells after exposure to extracts from the tested materials containing 10% and 15% of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (Fig. 15c, 15d). Moreover, the cells showed normal morphology. Both the MTT assay and Live/Dead staining indicated that biomaterials with these concentrations of Fe₃O₄ exhibited an increased biocompatibility, which was manifested as reduced cytotoxicity. A similar trend was observed in the test of direct biomaterial-cells contact. After 48 h of cell incubation on the biomaterials, microscopic observations revealed that hFOB cells had populated the surfaces of the biomaterials containing the highest concentrations of Fe₃O₄ (10% and 15% of Fe₃O₄), confirming the non-cytotoxicity of the materials (Fig. 16). The hFOB cells were alive (green fluorescence) and exhibited a flattened morphology, which suggested good cell adhesion to the biomaterials. It is worth noting that in the other material variants, the cells were also alive (green fluorescence), and no dead cells observed (absence of red fluorescence).

Fig. 16. Viability of human osteoblasts (hFOB 1.19 cells) cultured on the biomaterials. Live cells – green fluorescence; dead cells – red fluorescence. Magnification: 100x, scale bar: 150 μ m.

However, they displayed a round shape and abnormal morphology. These observations indicated that the Fe₃O₄ addition may positively modify the surfaces of the biomaterials, promoting cell adhesion. The conducted cell proliferation assay demonstrated that extracts from the developed biomaterials did not negatively affect the proliferation of hFOB cells. Both

on days 3 and 5, the number of cells incubated with the extracts was comparable to the control cells (those incubated in 10% culture medium) (Fig. 17a). However, CLSM staining revealed that with an increase in Fe_3O_4 concentration, the number of cells also increased (Fig. 17b).

Fig. 17. Quantitative (a) and qualitative (b) representation of the cell proliferation assay results. CLSM images, 200x magnification, scale bar 100 μm .

The *in vitro* biocompatibility studies conducted with human osteoblasts revealed that the PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 15% biomaterial most effectively supported both cell viability and cell proliferation, suggesting its potential for medical applications. Notably, the results indicated that cells adapted to the conditions created by the biomaterials over time. This is supported by the viability assay, which showed reduced cytotoxicity after 48 h compared to 24 h (in biomaterials containing 5%, 10%, and 15% of Fe_3O_4), and the proliferation assay, which demonstrated no negative impact of the biomaterials on cell growth. Furthermore, it is worth emphasizing that regardless of the *in vitro* biocompatibility test performed, all cells observed via CLSM were viable. While the PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 15% foam undoubtedly appeared to be the most promising, the potential utility of the other biomaterials cannot be definitively excluded.

4. Conclusions

Foam PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 composites with a wide range of magnetic component concentrations (1 - 30%) were successfully fabricated using the TIPS technique, supplemented

by the salt leaching process (SLP). Calcium hydroxyapatite and Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, with primary sizes of 20 nm and 80 nm, were synthesized through wet chemical methods, specifically co-precipitation and thermal decomposition, and subsequently incorporated into the PLLA matrix. The density of the hybrid materials ranged from 0.02 to 0.079 g/mL, depending on the inorganic content, while their porosity varied between 93% and 98% with a pore size of 330 μm . A decrease in the PLLA polymer decomposition temperature was observed due to the presence of Fe_3O_4 . Structural collapse of the porous microstructure occurred upon doping with 20% Fe_3O_4 (70% of fillers).

Energy conversion under alternating magnetic field (AMF), and near-infrared (NIR) irradiation (808, 880, 1122 nm) was thoroughly investigated in separate and synergistic modes. The results demonstrated the high responsiveness of the foams, characterized by rapid heating and the ability to reach biologically relevant temperatures in both dry and Ringer's solution-soaked composites. Upon materials characterization, the PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 with 15% of the magnetic component was chosen as the most reliable sample in terms of its microstructure, achievable T_{max} (AMF - 43.8°C, laser 45°C, dual mode - 58°C for soaked hybrids) as well as sufficient biocompatibility and cell adhesion toward hFOB line. Although higher heating effects were observed for the 20% and 30% of the Fe_3O_4 content in PLLA/HAP/ Fe_3O_4 foams, their microstructure collapse excluded them from consideration as a potential bone replacement material. Incorporating the cubic Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles into PLLA/HAP hybrids efficiently generates heat and significantly enhances the functional properties of foams, making them highly suitable for biomedical applications.

5. Acknowledgements

Financial support of PCI (Podkarpackie Centrum Innowacji) within project N3_032 'Multifunctional foams for temperature stimulated regenerative process of bone tissue' is gratefully acknowledged. R.P. was a holder of the SSHN scholarship funded by the French Government. Financial assistance was partially provided by Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland within DS2 project of Medical University of Lublin. D.Z. and Š. H. acknowledge the assistance provided by Advanced Multiscale Materials for Key Enabling Technologies project, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic Project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004558, co-funded by the European Union. D.Z. is also financially supported by Charles University Research Centre program No. UNCE/24/SCI/010.

6. Authors contribution statement

E.Z. preparation of foams, density, porosity, TGA, DSC, manuscript writing and editing. A.T. synthesis of Fe₃O₄ and HAP nanoparticles, XRD and FTIR measurements, data analysis, and manuscript editing. M.K.-G. TEM imaging, energy conversion measurements, and manuscript editing. P.K. SEM characterization, data analysis, and manuscript editing. J.-M. N. data analysis, manuscript writing, and editing. D.Z. and Š.H. magnetic measurements, data analysis, manuscript writing and editing. A.B.-R. and A.N. biological characterization of foams, data analysis, manuscript writing and editing. R.P. idea, conceptualization, data analysis, energy conversion analysis, manuscript writing, and editing.

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